

PERINATAL PATHOLOGY UNDER PANDEMIC CONDITIONS COVID-19

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7865881>

Abstract: COVID-19 infection diagnosed during pregnancy may have an adverse effect on the fetus. The article describes the results of the study of perinatal pathology after coronavirus infection in pregnant women. COVID-19 in early pregnancy is mainly complicated by non-progressive pregnancy, miscarriage, antenatal fetal death, and fetal malformations. The incidence of COVID-19 in later periods leads to intrauterine pneumonia, respiratory distress syndrome, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy and sepsis. In both groups, the birth of newborns with low weight for gestational age was noted.

Key words: COVID-19, pregnancy, newborns, childbirth, intrauterine pneumonia.

Introduction.

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pneumonia outbreak, the sudden onset of symptoms of respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has been a danger to the population, especially for pregnant women and their newborns, for 3 years now. At present, there are few data on the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy, childbirth, the fetus and the postpartum period. According to researchers, cases of infection in newborns have been recorded. Taking into account all the risk factors for the development of complications, it was necessary to study the condition of newborns from mothers who had COVID-19 during pregnancy.

The purpose of the study: to study the features of the neonatal period from mothers who had a coronavirus infection during pregnancy.

Materials and methods.

The study was conducted in the obstetric-gynecological complex of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy from November 15, 2020 to December 15, 2021. 229 pregnant women and their newborns were examined. The subjects were divided into 3 groups: group 1 consisted of 75 newborns who had COVID-19 from their mothers in the first trimester; group 2 included 84 newborns from mothers who had COVID-19 in the third trimester; group 3, control - 70 newborns from healthy women. A general clinical examination, PCR (SARS-CoV-2) of pregnant women and their newborns, Doppler blood flow in the mother-placenta-fetus system, as well as an assessment of the condition of newborns from mothers who had COVID-19 were carried out.

Results and discussion.

The influence of coronavirus infection on the development of the fetus in the womb was studied. The incidence of COVID-19 before 12 weeks of pregnancy led to spontaneous abortion in 15.9%, while non-developing pregnancy was diagnosed in 24%. Analyzing the results, we revealed the aggressive impact of the COVID-19 virus on fetal development. In

13.3% (10) of patients of the first group, pregnancy was terminated due to malformations, in the form of anencephaly in 5.3% (4), abrachia 2.67% (2), heart defects 5.3% (4). No such complications were found in the second group. Antenatal fetal death in those who had COVID-19 before 12 weeks of pregnancy was 6.82% (5), while in the second group this figure was 5% (4). Therefore, COVID-19 infection in early pregnancy has a more aggressive effect on the fetus.

It was noted an increase in the frequency of preterm birth after infection during pregnancy. It was found that every fourth woman of the first and second groups had a premature birth, while this figure in the control group was 10.6%.

There have also been cases of coronavirus infection in newborns from mothers who had COVID-19 during childbirth. 3.6% had positive results of PCR (SARS-CoV-2), which is apparently due to infection in the first minutes of birth by contact.

The study revealed that the state of newborns according to the APGAR scale in the studied groups does not differ much from the control. Newborns of the first and second groups did not show any signs of intrauterine infection at birth and were assessed satisfactorily according to the APGAR scale. However, noteworthy is the fact that 21.4% (18) of the subjects in the first group had signs of respiratory failure in the first 2 hours and 9.5% (8) on 2-3 days after birth. Respiratory failure was diagnosed in 33.3% (25) of the newborns in the first group, in 45.24% (38) of the newborns in the second group, while in the control group this figure was 11.4%. Respiratory failure manifested itself in the form of cyanosis of the skin in 26.6% and 35.7% in the first and second groups, retraction of the intercostal spaces in 30.6% and 38.1%, shortness of breath in 33.3% and 42.8% , swelling of the wings of the nose during breathing - in 28.6% and 40.5%, moaning - in 30.6% and 40.5% and low saturation - in 33.3% and 45.24%.

The study also identified cases of birth of newborns with low birth weight for gestational age. Low body weight was recorded in every fourth newborn of the second and first groups, while in the control group this figure was 6.67%. It should be noted that high rates of births of children with very low birth weight are also associated with an increase in the number of preterm births. It is noteworthy that in newborns from mothers who had coronavirus infection during pregnancy, intrauterine pneumonia was observed three times more than in the control group. Respiratory distress syndrome was diagnosed more often in newborns from mothers of the first group (42.3%). Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy was detected in almost equal amounts in the main groups (26.4%; 18.4%). General clinical studies have shown that anemia, hepatosplenomegaly, and sepsis were diagnosed mainly in newborns in the first and second groups, which once again proves the negative impact of coronavirus infection on the condition of the fetus.

Thus, COVID-19 has an aggressive impact on the course of pregnancy, childbirth, the condition of the fetus and newborn.

Conclusions.

The course of pregnancy in women who have undergone COVID-19 before 12 weeks of gestation is complicated by spontaneous miscarriage, the development of fetal defects, antenatal fetal death, and every fourth pregnancy has a non-developing pregnancy.

It was revealed that respiratory failure is observed three times more often in newborns born from mothers who had COVID-19 in the first trimester and four times more in newborns from

mothers who had a coronavirus infection in the third trimester, compared with the control group.

It has been established that the birth of children with low weight for gestational age is twice as high in newborns of the first and second groups, compared with newborns of the third group. This is due to a violation of the uteroplacental-fetal circulation during pregnancy and the aggressive effect of the SARS-Cov-2 virus on fetal development.

It was found that intrauterine pneumonia occurs three times more often in newborn mothers who had COVID-19 in the third trimester than in newborns of the control group. Respiratory distress syndrome of newborns and hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy occurs two and three times more often in newborns of the first group, while in the second group this figure was 32.40% and 18.40%, respectively. Complications such as hepatosplenomegaly, sepsis, anemia were observed more often in newborns born from mothers who had a coronavirus infection only in the third trimester.

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